

Assessments of Organic Carbon Stocks in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists

Guideline and Protocols

Version 1.1

10.10.2025

Citation: Weigelhofer, G., Wijffels, O., Rosenberger, C., Ramadan, H., Alphart, J., Novkovic, M., Cvijanović D. (2025) Assessments of Organic Carbon stocks in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists. Guideline and Protocols. Horizon Europe Project Restore4Life (101112736). [10.5281/zenodo.17328601](https://zenodo.org/record/17328601)

Content

CHAPTER 1: BACKGROUND	3
CHAPTER 2: WETLANDS AS ESSENTIAL CARBON STORES HELP REGULATE THE CLIMATE	4
CHAPTER 3: SOIL ORGANIC CARBON IN SOILS WITH SHALLOW ORGANIC LAYER (FLOODPLAIN FOREST, MEADOWS)	5
3.1. PROTOCOL	5
3.2. CALCULATIONS	8
3.3. FOR SCIENTISTS	19
CHAPTER 4: SOIL ORGANIC CARBON IN SOILS WITH DEEP ORGANIC LAYER (PEATLANDS)	20
4.1. PROTOCOL	20
4.2. FOR SCIENTISTS	4
CHAPTER 5: ORGANIC CARBON IN TREE BIOMASS	5
5.1. PROTOCOL TREE HEIGHT AND CIRCUMFERENCE	5
5.2. FOR SCIENTISTS	8
5.3. PROTOCOL BITTERLICH METHOD	11

CHAPTER 1: BACKGROUND

Monitoring Ecosystem Services (ES) provided by wetlands is crucial for assessing the state of the wetlands, their changes over time, and the impacts of conservation and restoration measures. The engagement of non-experts as Citizen Scientists can support this ES monitoring by delivering large amounts of data otherwise not (easily) available. Additionally, Citizen Science helps raise awareness among local people about the significance of wetlands for human well-being, thereby enhancing citizens' stewardship.

In the Horizon Europe Project **RESTORE4LIFE**, 101112736 (<https://restore4life.eu/>), we have created a **toolbox for monitoring ES of wetlands** (Deliverable D3.5), covering both geospatial and on-the-ground methods (publicly available from Dec 2025 on our webpage and Zenodo). One focus was on developing Citizen Science protocols for on-the-ground measurements that provide reliable and valuable data for wetland assessments. Various Citizen Scientists helped us test the developed protocols regarding their intelligibility, user-friendliness, and applicability before release. To assess the quality and explanatory power of the data collected by Citizen Scientists, we compared them with data collected by scientists using more advanced methods. The results of these quality checks can be found in our toolbox D3.5.

The following topics were covered and published separately: (1) water quality, (2) organic carbon storage in tree biomass and wetland soils, (3) plant diversity, and (4) recreational and educational services. Each published document consists of several parts: Citizen Scientists' protocol(s) for assessing data in the field; Citizen Scientists' protocol(s) for indoor analyses (if applicable); Citizen Scientists' protocol(s) for calculations (if applicable); and a guideline for scientists on further data processing.

The current document addresses the **Potential of wetlands to store organic carbon in above- and below-ground biomass**.

CHAPTER 2: WETLANDS AS ESSENTIAL CARBON STORES HELP REGULATE THE CLIMATE

Wetlands are dynamic ecosystems that store significant amounts of organic carbon in tree biomass and soils. This is due to the high productivity of the vegetation and the frequent water saturation of the soils, which slows the decomposition of organic material, helping preserve carbon.

This storage helps **regulate atmospheric CO₂ levels and mitigate global warming**.

Wetland degradation occurs due to drainage for agriculture or development, damming or water diversion, overgrazing, logging, or peat extraction. These activities disturb waterlogged conditions, which are crucial for storing carbon. As a consequence of wetland degradation, wetlands **change from carbon sinks to carbon sources**. Drainage of peatlands, for example, can release up to 20–40 tonnes of CO₂ per hectare per year.

This makes **wetland conservation and restoration** essential strategies in global climate mitigation efforts.

Your contribution to assessing the organic carbon storage in wetlands significantly supports wetland restoration.

Thank you

CHAPTER 3: SOIL ORGANIC CARBON IN SOILS WITH SHALLOW ORGANIC LAYER (FLOODPLAIN FOREST, MEADOWS)

3.1. PROTOCOL

MATERIALS:

- ❖ Soil sampler (drill) or shovel
- ❖ Plastic bags (1 L)
- ❖ Spoons
- ❖ Measuring stick
- ❖ Small water bottle
- ❖ if possible, small cool box
- ❖ **For indoor analyses:** mason jar, balance, oven (or dry place); aluminum foil (for oven drying), two measuring cylinders;
- ❖ **For advanced indoor analyses:** balance, clean 500 mL plastic beakers, coffee filters, funnel, pH test strips, nitrate and phosphate test kits

OUTDOOR TASKS:

1. Site characteristics:

Use your smartphone's GPS to determine your location's coordinates and record them in the form. Take a picture of the site.

2. Sampling:

Remove plants and litter from the ground. If you have a soil drill, drive the drill to a depth of 15 cm and carefully draw the soil sample. If you have a shovel, dig a hole of approx. 15 cm depth and 20x20 cm area into the soil so that you can see the vertical layers.

3. Soil profile:

Measure and record the depth of the upper dark (organic-rich) layer. Take a picture of the soil profile together with the measuring stick.

4. Soil type:

Carefully remove a sample the size of a walnut from the lower, **brighter layer**. If the sample is dry, wet it slightly. Knead the sample between your fingers into a sphere. Then, try to make a cylinder. Now, rub the sample carefully between your fingers. Based on your observations, determine the soil type according to the table given below and record it in the soil form.

5. Sampling for indoor analyses:

Place one fresh sample from the upper dark layer and one from the lower lighter soil layer in separate plastic bags. The samples should be the size of an apricot. **Label** the bags with the location's name, the date, and the layer (upper/lower). Store the samples in a cool, dark box or bag until further analysis in the lab.

INDOOR TASKS:

Always keep the label attached to the sample so that you can identify it!

6. Measure the volume of the sample:

Place the closed plastic bag with the sample into the measuring cylinder. Fill a second cylinder with water and note the starting volume. Now, pour water from the second cylinder into the first cylinder until the soil sample is entirely covered. Record the volume of water added and the total volume (soil + water). Subtract the water volume from the total volume to estimate the sample volume.

7. Dry weight and moisture content:

Remove the soil from the bag and weigh it (wet weight). Dry the samples in an oven (75°C for 24 hours) or the sun (for four days) and weigh them again (dry weight).

8. Organic content – Jar experiment

Fill the remaining soil sample into a mason jar (leave one spoonful aside for the advanced analysis). Then, pour water into the jar. Shake for 3 minutes and let the soil particles settle for 1-2 days.

Observe the layers that form: The organic matter floats on top of the water (dark colour). At the bottom, you can see the mineral particles: the lowest is sand, followed by silt and then clay (see picture).

Measure the height of each layer with a ruler.

Remove the organic layer on top of the water carefully using a spoon or forceps, **dry** and **weigh** it.

Finally, dry the remaining sample in the jar and weigh it.

ADVANCED INDOOR TASKS:

9. Soil chemistry:

Add one spoonful of soil to approximately 50 mL of distilled water and stir for 1 minute. Filter the mixture through a coffee filter into a clean beaker. Wash the funnel and use new coffee filters for each new sample.

Use test strips to measure various parameters such as pH, nitrate, and hardness.

3.2. CALCULATIONS

1. Calculate soil moisture content SM (%):

Subtract the dry weight of the sample from the initial weight to get the water weight. Then, divide the water weight by the initial weight and multiply by 100 to get the soil moisture (in %):

$$\text{Soil moisture SM (\%)} = (\text{Wet weight} - \text{dry weight}) / \text{wet weight} \times 100$$

2. Calculate soil bulk density BD (g/dm³):

Important: You have probably measured the volume in litres or millilitres. Convert volumes into cubic decimeters (dm³) for the calculations (1L = 1 dm³). Then, divide the dry weight (g) by the sample volume (dm³).

$$\text{Soil bulk density BD (g/dm}^3\text{)} = \text{Dry weight (g)} / \text{sample volume (dm}^3\text{)}$$

3. Calculate percentage of soil components (%) – Jar experiment:

In addition to the estimation in the field, you can use the data from the jar experiment to determine the soil type. Divide the height of each layer by the total height and multiply it by 100:

$$\text{Height of sand layer} / \text{total height of soil layers} \times 100 = \% \text{ sand}$$

$$\text{Height of silt layer} / \text{total height of soil layers} \times 100 = \% \text{ silt}$$

$$\text{Height of clay} / \text{total height of soil layers} \times 100 = \% \text{ clay}$$

4. Calculating the Organic carbon content OC (%) – Jar experiment:

Calculate the **total dry weight TW** of the sample in the jar by adding the dry weight of the organic matter to the dry weight of the rest of the sample.

$$\text{Total dry weight TW (g)} = \text{Dry weight OM (g)} + \text{Dry weight rest of sample (g)}$$

Divide the dry weight of the organic matter by 2 to get the amount of **organic carbon OC**. Most organic matter has a carbon content of around 50%.

$$\text{Organic carbon OC (g)} = \text{Dry weight OM (g)} / 2$$

Finally, divide the organic carbon OC by the total dry weight TW

$$\text{Percentage of organic carbon OC}^1 = \text{dry weight OC} / \text{total dry weight TW}$$

5. Calculating the Soil Organic Carbon Storage (kg/m²)

Multiply the soil bulk density (BD) by the percentage of organic carbon OC to get the organic carbon concentration (g/dm³).

$$\text{Organic carbon concentration OCC (g/dm}^3\text{)} = \text{Soil bulk density BD (g/dm}^3\text{)} \times \text{Percentage of Organic carbon OC}$$

¹ The percentage is given as a dimensionless fraction here. So, 20% = 0.2, 50% = 0.5, 100% = 1.

Now, calculate the **average organic carbon storage per square meter OC_{storage} (kg/m^2)** by multiplying the carbon concentration by the depth of the organic layer at your site (m).

$$OC_{\text{storage}} (\text{kg}/\text{m}^2) = \text{Organic carbon concentration OCC (g}/\text{dm}^3) \times \text{Depth (m)}$$

Note: To maintain consistency, remember that converting from g/dm^3 to g/m^3 involves multiplying by 1000, and converting grams to kilograms involves dividing by 1000. These factors cancel each other out in the final formula.

Soil Form

Name			
Date		Time	
Location		Vegetation ¹	
GPS		Depth of upper dark layer (cm)	
	Upper dark layer	Lower brighter layer	
Form into a sphere			
Form into a cylinder			
Soil feeling			
Stickiness			
Soil type			
Moisture content (%)			
Bulk density			
Sand (%) (Jar exp.)			
Silt (%) (Jar exp.)			
Clay (%) (Jar exp.)			
Organic Carbon Content (%)			
Soil carbon storage (kg/m ²)			
Comments			

¹ (Coniferous forest, deciduous forest, wet meadow, dry meadow, ...)

Soil type test

Soil type	Form to a sphere 	Soil feeling	Sticks to your fingers	
Sand	Not possible	crumbles	Rough, small grains can be felt and seen	no
Silt	Not possible	crumbles	Like velvet or flour, no grains visible	Only in the grooves of the finger
Loam	Difficult, easily crumbles	Small roll possible (pencil-thick), then crumbles	Soil consists of approx. 50% small grains and 50% very fine material	Only in the grooves of the finger
Clay	Easily possible	Easily possible	Sample shines; no grains perceptible, feels soapy-greasy	Yes, strongly

3.3. FOR SCIENTISTS

Soil laboratory analyses in the lab:

- ❖ **Moisture content:** If you use zipper bags, the wet and dry weight can be better determined in the lab due to the scales' sensitivity there. We recommend direct weighing by the CS only when the samples need to be stored longer and may lose moisture content.
- ❖ **Organic content via combustion at 450°C:** CS could also do this in an oven at 250 to 300°C. However, we do not recommend it as soil with a high organic content may catch fire. Also, ash may get lost if the samples are not properly handled. Finally, the balance must be very fine to obtain the correct data.
- ❖ **pH:** pH is easy to determine by CS via test strips. Here, the CS can also use fresh samples.
- ❖ **Nutrients:** We tried to use water nutrient test kits on soil leachates. Phosphate worked quite well but nitrate did not work. The reason could be the slightly brownish colouring of the leachate, which may make it difficult to determine the colour correctly. This is more of an educational activity than data collection. Regarding test strips, we compared several products and found significant differences. Thus, we recommend testing the commercially available products against lab analyses before distributing them to CS.

REFERENCES

www.bettersoils.com.au; 1.7.2024

<https://expedition-erdreich.bonares.de/>; 1.7.2024

https://extension.purdue.edu/county/vanderburgh/_media/collecting-soil-samples-for-testing-ho-71-w.pdf; 1.7.2024

CHAPTER 4: SOIL ORGANIC CARBON IN SOILS WITH DEEP ORGANIC LAYER (PEATLANDS)

4.1. PROTOCOL

MATERIALS:

- ❖ 2 m steel rods: if you use threaded rods (M8 x 1000mm) and connecting nuts (M8), you can extend the rod as long as needed
- ❖ Coloured tape
- ❖ Shovel
- ❖ Plastic bags (1 L)
- ❖ Measuring stick
- ❖ if possible, a small cool box

For indoor analysis: 2 measuring cylinders, oven or dry place, aluminum foil (for oven drying), balance (scale)

OUTDOOR TASKS:

1. Site characteristics:

Use your smartphone's GPS to determine your location's coordinates and record them in the **soil form**. Take a picture of the site.

2. Peat depth:

Insert the threaded rods length-wise into the peat until you feel a markedly increased resistance. Mark the top of the peat layer on the rod with the tape, then remove the rod and measure the length. This is the depth of the peat.

3. Peat degradation:

Dig your hand approx. 10 cm into the peat and take a sample of peat slightly larger than a golf ball. Squeeze it hard in your clenched fist. Determine the value of H0 to H10 on the Von Post scale given below.

4. Sampling:

Place a handful of the upper peat layer in a zipper bag, close it, and label the bag. Place the bag in a box and store it under cool conditions until further analyses in the lab/at home.

INDOOR TASKS:

5. Organic content:

Take the peat sample out of the bag and **weigh it (wet weight)**.

Then, place the sample in one **measuring cylinder**. Fill a second cylinder with water and note the starting volume. Now, pour water from the second cylinder into the first cylinder until the sample is entirely covered. Record the volume of water added and the total volume (soil + water). Subtract the water volume from the total volume to estimate the sample volume.

Finally, dry the peat sample in an oven or a dry place and **weigh it again (dry weight)**.

SOIL FORM

Name			
Date		Time	
Location		GPS	
Depth of the peat (cm)			
Degree of Humification (Van Post-Scale)			
Sample volume (L)			
Wet weight (g)			
Dry weight (g)			

VON POST HUMIFICATION SCALE (source FAO, 2011)

The von Post scale is a field test to rank organic soils by degree of humification (decomposition). The 10 steps correspond to percentage of decomposition i.e. 1 = 10% or undecomposed plant material, and 10 = 100% decomposed or colloidal, such as the highest caloric value burnable black peat.

SYMBOL	DESCRIPTION
H1	Completely undecomposed peat which, when squeezed, releases almost clear water. Plant remains easily identifiable. No amorphous material present.
H2	Almost entirely undecomposed peat which, when squeezed, releases clear or yellowish water. Plant remains still easily identifiable. No amorphous material present.
H3	Very slightly decomposed peat which, when squeezed, releases muddy brown water, but from which no peat passes between the fingers. Plant remains still identifiable, and no amorphous material present.
H4	Slightly decomposed peat which, when squeezed, releases very muddy brown water. No peat is passed between the fingers but plant remains are slightly pasty and have lost some of their identifiable features.
H5	Moderately decomposed peat which, when squeezed, releases very muddy water with a very small amount of amorphous granular peat escaping between the fingers. The structure of the plant remains is quite indistinct although it is still possible to recognize certain features. The residue is very pasty.
H6	Moderately highly decomposed peat with a very indistinct plant structure. When squeezed, about one-third of the peat escapes between the fingers. The residue is very pasty but shows the plant structure more distinctly than before squeezing.
H7	Highly decomposed peat. Contains a lot of amorphous material with very faintly recognizable plant structure. When squeezed, about one-half of the peat escapes between the fingers. The water, if any is released, is very dark and almost pasty.
H8	Very highly decomposed peat with a large quantity of amorphous material and very indistinct plant structure. When squeezed, about two-thirds of the peat escapes between the fingers. A small quantity of pasty water may be released. The plant material remaining in the hand consists of residues such as roots and fibres that resist decomposition.
H9	Practically fully decomposed peat in which there is hardly any recognizable plant structure. When squeezed, it is a fairly uniform paste.
H10	Completely decomposed peat with no discernible plant structure. When squeezed, all the wet peat escapes between the fingers.

4.2. FOR SCIENTISTS

The project “Tracking the Color of Peatlands” (University of Plymouth) monitors changes in peatland green leaf phenology (i.e. how the peatlands change colour over the course of the year) using smartphone photography and colour recognition. Thus, CS do not need to go on the peatland but can track changes from walking paths.

<https://www.plymouth.ac.uk/research/plymouth-peatland-research-group/tracking-the-colour-of-peatlands-project> 11.10.2025

CHAPTER 5: ORGANIC CARBON IN TREE BIOMASS

5.1. PROTOCOL TREE HEIGHT AND CIRCUMFERENCE

MATERIALS:

- ❖ Flexible 2 m tape
- ❖ Smartphone
- ❖ Stick of at least an arm's length
- ❖ Tree biomass form

OUTDOOR TASKS:

1. Site Characterisation:

Select 3-5 sites within your survey area. The sites should be easily accessible and representative of the region. Each site should have an area of approximately 20 m in length and 10 m in width. For tree height estimations, you must see the entire tree from approximately 20 m. Thus, in dense forests, select a site along a path. **Take a picture** of each site and note the **GPS data** and the date and time of the survey in the “Tree biomass” form.

2. Circumference and tree species:

Measure the circumference of each tree within this site via the “Diameter-at-Breast-Height method” (see below). **Identify each tree species** using the App "Flora incognita". Note both the species names and circumferences in the “Tree biomass” form.

3. Tree height:

Select 1-2 trees of average height. Estimate the tree height using the “Triangle method” (see below). With the mean height and the exact circumference, we can estimate the tree's biomass.

"Diameter-at-Breast-Height" Method to determine the circumference of a tree

The "Diameter-at-Breast-Height" method is a simple procedure that quickly provides information about a tree trunk's mean circumference and diameter. It can be used for both living and dead trees.

- a. Stand in front of the tree and have your measuring tape ready. If the tree is on a slope, stand between the uphill and the downhill side of the tree.
- b. Measure 1.37 meters upward from the ground. A height of 1.37 meters represents the mean tree diameter. If the tree stands on a slope, measure from the mid-point between uphill and downhill (see picture).
- c. Now place the measuring tape at the measured height around the trunk and measure the circumference of the tree trunk. Ensure the measuring tape is tightly held against the bark and wraps as circularly around the trunk as possible.
- d. Calculate the mean tree diameter by dividing the measured circumference by 3.14.

“Triangle Method” to determine the Tree Height

The Forester's Triangle method allows you to quickly and easily determine the height of trees.

- a. Choose 2-3 trees that are easy to access. It is essential that you can see the entire tree from bottom to top. Make sure that the surrounding terrain is level.
- b. To estimate the tree height, you need a long, straight stick. The length of the stick should equal the length of your outstretched arm.
- c. Hold the stick with your outstretched arm in a vertical position so that a right-angled triangle is formed between your arm and the stick (see picture). Stand in front of the chosen tree and walk backward from the tree in a straight line until the length of your stick roughly matches the height of the tree. From your position, the base of the stick just above your hand should be approximately the same height as the base of the trunk. The stick's tip should be roughly the same height as the treetop.
- d. Once the stick and tree are equivalent, mark the spot where you are standing and measure the distance to the tree. You can do this either with a long (20-30 m) measuring tape or by pacing the distance between this spot and the tree. For pacing, take as large steps as possible, as they roughly correspond to one meter, allowing you to estimate the distance to the tree better.
- e. The distance measured corresponds to the height of the tree.

5.2. FOR SCIENTISTS

You can estimate the carbon stock and sequestration of a tree via its height, diameter, and density using the following formulas:

1. **Total Volume V:**

$$V (m^3) = 3.14 \times r^2 \times h \times 1.4$$

Where r=radius of the stem at 1.37 m height (m) and h=tree height (m). The factor 1.4 accounts for the root and canopy biomass (Shadman et al. 2022).

2. **Total Carbon Content (OC):**

For the total carbon content, multiply the tree's total volume by the wood density and the organic carbon content. The density of dry wood depends on the tree species (see list below). For rough estimations, take a mean of 530 kg/m³. The carbon content is 50% of the dry mass.

$$OC (kg) = Total Volume \times Density \times 0.5$$

3. **CO₂ sequestered:**

The weight of CO₂ sequestered in trees is determined by the ratio of CO₂ to C, which is 44/12 = 3.67. Multiply TC by 3.67 to estimate the CO₂ sequestered.

$$CO_2 \text{ sequ (kg)} = OC \times 3.67$$

Note that this value represents the CO₂ sequestered in the entire lifetime of the tree. To ascertain the annual CO₂ sequestration rate, divide the total CO₂ sequestered by the tree's age (if available).

4. **Ellenberg's indicator values**

These indicators provide information about the ecological requirements of tree species regarding light, temperature, moisture content, soil acidity, and Nitrogen

content, to characterize the site. Unfortunately, these indicators are available only in German and only for Central Europe at <https://statedv.boku.ac.at/zeigerwerte/>.

The Flora incognita also offers species traits in the descriptions of the species.

REFERENCES

<https://bigtrees.forestry.ubc.ca/measuring-trees/>. 27.06.2024

Vries, W. et al. (2003). *Intensive Monitoring of Forest Ecosystems in Europe: Technical Report 2003*.

Shadman, S, et al. (2022) *The carbon sequestration potential of urban public parks of densely populated cities to improve environmental sustainability. Sustainable Energy Technologies and Assessments 52, 102064.*

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2022.102064>.

Table 5.6 Stem wood densities per tree species that were used to calculate carbon pools in trees

Tree species Group	Included tree species	Wood density (kg m ⁻³)
Salix	Salix alba, Salix caprea, Salix cinerea, Salix eleagnos, Salix fragilis, Salix sp.	330
Thuja	Thuja sp.	350
Cedrus	Cedrus atlantica, Cedrus deodara	400
Abies/Populus	Abies alba, Abies borisii-regis, Abies cephalonica, Abies grandis, Abies nordmanniana, Abies pinsapo, Abies procera, Pinus radiata, Pinus strobus, Populus alba, Populus canescens, Populus hybrides, Populus nigra, Populus tremula,	410
Picea	Picea abies, Picea omorika	400
Picea sitchensis	Picea sitchensis	350
Tsuga	Tsuga sp.	440
Other conifers	Cupressus lusitanica, Cupressus sempervirens, Juniperus communis, Juniperus oxycedrus, Juniperus phoenicea, Juniperus sabina, Juniperus thurifera, Taxus baccata, Chamaecyparis lawsoniana, Other conifers	450 ¹
Pseudotsuga	Pseudotsuga menziesii	470
Pinus/Tilia	Pinus brutia, Pinus canariensis, Pinus cembra, Pinus contorta, Pinus halepensis, Pinus heldreichii, Pinus leucodermis, Pinus mugo, Pinus nigra, Pinus pinaster, Pinus pinea, Pinus sylvestris, Pinus uncinata, Tilia cordata, Tilia platyphyllos,	490
Alnus	Alnus cordata, Alnus glutinosa, Alnus incana, Alnus viridis	510
Prunus/Larix	Prunus avium, Prunus dulcis, Prunus padus, Prunus serotina, Larix decidua, Larix kaempferi	550
Juglans	Juglans nigra, Juglans regia	560
Olea/Platanus	Olea europaea, Platanus orientalis	580
Acer	Acer campestre, Acer monspessulanum, Acer opalus, Acer platanoides, Castanea sativa	590
Other broadleaves	Buxus sempervirens, Ilex aquifolium, Tamarix africana, Arbutus unedo, Arbutus andrachne, Ceratonia siliqua, Cercis siliquastrum, Erica arborea, Erica scoparia, Erica manipuliflora, Phillyrea latifolia, Phillyrea angustifolia, Pistacia lentiscus, Pistacia terebinthus, Rhamnus oleoides, Rhamnus alaternus, Betula tortuosa, Ceratonia siliqua (same as 75), Crataegus monogyna, Other broadleaves	595 ¹
Betula	Betula pendula, Betula pubescens	610
Acer/Ulmus	Acer pseudoplatanus, Ulmus glabra, Ulmus laevis, Ulmus minor	640
Fraxinus/Quercus	Fraxinus angustifolia, Fraxinus excelsior, Fraxinus ornus, Quercus cerris, Quercus coccifera, Quercus faginea, Quercus frainetto, Quercus fruticosa, Quercus ilex, Quercus macrolepis, Quercus petraea, Quercus pubescens, Quercus pyrenaica, Quercus robur, Quercus rotundifolia, Quercus rubra, Quercus suber, Quercus trojana	600
Fagus	Fagus moesiaca, Fagus orientalis, Fagus sylvatica	680
Eucalyptus	Eucalyptus sp., Malus domestica, Pyrus communis, Laurus nobilis, Myrtus communis	700
Sorbus	Sorbus aria, Sorbus aucuparia, Sorbus domestica, Sorbus torminalis	730
Robinia pseudacacia	Robinia pseudacacia	740
Carpinus	Carpinus betulus, Carpinus orientalis, Corylus avellana, Ostrya carpinifolia	790

¹ Stem densities for the considered other conifers and other broadleaves have been set at the average of all species

Wood densities for common trees. From Vries et al 2003

5.3. PROTOCOL BITTERLICH METHOD

The Bitterlich method (1984) is a forest measurement technique used to determine the basal area of trees per hectare (m²/ha). This method involves selecting multiple systematically distributed points in the forest. The technique can substitute the measurement of the circumference and be used to calculate the existing timber volume if multiplied by the average tree height.

MATERIALS:

- ❖ Measuring tape (100 cm)
- ❖ Relascope: 50 cm rope and 2x4 cm plate (or you use your arm length and your thumb)
- ❖ Smartphone

❖ OUTDOOR TASKS:

1. Determine the **basal area count factor CF**:

$$CF = (W \times 50 \div L)^2$$

where W is the width of the relascope (or thumb) and L is the length of the rope (or arm). Example: For a stick with a length of 50 cm and a plate width of 2 cm, the count factor is calculated as follows (calculate in the same way for arm and thumb):

$$(2 \text{ cm} \times 50 \div 50 \text{ cm})^2 = 2^2 = 4$$

2. Select the first **sampling point** in the forest. Hold one end of the rope to your eye and attach the other end to the plate in a horizontal line. The rope is fully stretched.

3. Now rotate in a circle and **count all trees that appear as wide or wider than the plate** as follows:
- If the stem of the tree is visually wider than the plate, the tree is 'in' and assigned a count of 1.
 - If the stem of the tree matches the width of the plate, the tree is borderline and is assigned a count of 0.5.
 - If the stem of the tree is narrower than the instrument sight, the tree is 'out' and is not counted.

Repeat for at least 4 points and calculate the average number of trees.

4. Calculate the basal area:

$$\text{Basal area (m}^2\text{/ha)} = \text{Total number of trees} \times \text{CF}$$

5. Calculate the timber volume:

$$\text{Timber volume (m}^3\text{/ha)} = \text{Basal area} \times \text{average tree height} \times \text{form factor}$$

Use 0.5 for the form factor (Lockow, 2022)

For estimating the average tree height, see description of triangle method.

References:

Bitterlich,W., 1948: Die Winkelzählprobe. Allgemeine Forst- und Holzwirtschaftliche Zeitung, 59. Jahrg., Folge 1/2 vom Jänner 1948, Verlag Georg Fromme & Co., Wien.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF01821439>

Lockow, K.-W. (2022). *Waldbestandsmessung—Stichprobenverfahren—Wachstumsmodellierung*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-662-63061-7_2

Rédei, K., Ábri, T., Szabó, F., & Keserű, Z. (2020). Angle-count sampling method for estimating forest stand volume—a practical approach. DOI: 10.34101/ACTAAGRAR/2/7900

<https://cdn.cyfoethnaturiol.cymru/688310/template-diy-tree-measuring-kit.pdf>
11.10.2025

Look also for videos in the internet explaining the forestry techniques